

An Investigation of Domestic Tourists' Satisfaction with Son Tra Night Market, Da Nang – Viet Nam

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ABSTRACT

This paper employs theoretical bases from previous research findings by Parasuraman et. al, Zeithaml and Bitner, and other experimental research publications to analyse domestic tourists' satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang city-Viet Nam. With primary data from questionnaire for 270 domestic tourists visiting Son Tra Night market, using Likert-scale quantitative analysis techniques of scale reliability; exploratory factor analysis; and multiple regression analysis, the findings indicate that all 8 factors, namely Local specialities; Safety – Security; Landscape environment; Entertainment services; Products; Infrastructure; Service attitude; and Price, have positive effects on domestic tourists' satisfaction with Son Tra Night market – in Da Nang, Viet Nam.

KEYWORDS: Tourist destination; Son Tra Night market, Da Nang-Viet Nam; Satisfaction; Domestic tourists

I. INTRODUCTION

Satisfaction has a great impact on consumer behaviour. In a research by (Litvin, et al., 2008), satisfaction is the main driver determining the consumer behaviour; this finding is in line with that of (Hultman, et al., 2015). Research data on consumer behaviour is a major base for businesses to develop their marketing plan (Machleit & Mantel, 2001). In the field of tourism, (Hosany, et al., 2006) indicated that satisfaction with tourist destination is a competitive advantage to attract tourists. (Valentina, et al., 2015) found that tourists' satisfaction with destination experience contributes to their loyalty to the destination; also, research data on tourist satisfaction is an important base for administrators to implement improvement plans to attract more tourists. Accordingly, research on tourist satisfaction with destination is an essential indicator for goods and service providers. In Viet Nam, research on tourist satisfaction with destination is still limited with just a few publications namely: (Trang & Loan, 2012) in Soc Trang – Viet Nam; (Thinh & Huy, 2014) in Ninh Kieu, Can Tho-Viet Nam, (Tuan, 2015) in Ho Chi Minh City – Viet Nam; (Ly, 2021) in Du Nhom – Ninh Binh. Therefore, an investigation of tourist satisfaction with destination is really necessary for Viet Nam.

Da Nang, Viet Nam was re-established on January 1st 1997, and has become one the five centrally-controlled

municipalities ever since, set to be the key socio-economic development centre in the Central and Highlands region (Yeu, 1996). On October 16th 2003, the Politburo issued Resolution No. 33-NQ/TW on direction and tasks to develop Da Nang by 2020 with leading economic structure in the order of: Service, Industry, and Agriculture-Forestry, focusing on “Strongly invest in tourism as a spear-head economic sector of the city; build Da Nang into a major tourism centre of Viet Nam, a hub for transshipment, transit and exchange of service and goods in the Central and Highlands region” (Manh, 2023).

The development of tourism is a political task which is suitable with natural characteristics of Da Nang. In addition to exploiting natural advantages for tourism development, Da Nang has developed a variety of tourism programmes and events such as Da Nang Fireworks Festival, Linh Ung Pagoda, etc. to diversify tourist experience. On September 2nd 2018, the Son Tra Night market was open under Decision No. 3436/QĐ-UBND issued by the Da Nang People's Committee (Quyet, 2018) as a tourist destination to contribute to the city socio-economic development strategy. After four years, the Son Tra Night market has contributed to diversifying tourism products and attracted a variety of tourists to Da Nang. During the time of COVID-19 pandemic complication, however, the Son Tra Night market was temporarily closed from time to time.

The Son Tra Night market has gone back to business as usual since late 2021. It is necessary to employ a systematic and detailed assessment to propose feasible solutions to improve service quality and enhance the role of Son Tra Night market in attracting tourists to Da Nang. So far, research and reports on operation of the market have been developed from an administrative management perspective based on statistical data of tourist number and businesses at the market. Accordingly, this article, using quantitative analysis method, focuses on investigating systematically the service quality at the market to research levels of satisfaction of domestic tourists to the Son Tra Night market. The findings will be a reliable experimental source of reference for Da Nang government, businesses, and related media agencies to develop improvement plans to upgrade services and enhance communications to leverage the Son Tra Night market as a must-see destination in terms of tourist attraction and retention.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Customer satisfaction with night market

According to (Yu, 2004), night market is a place located in one or more streets for tourists to gather at night time to experience or consume food or shop for CDs, clothes, antiques, books, or small devices, etc. Night market plays an important role in facilitating local economic development. It also provides business locations which do not require too much investment and complicated technological equipment (Liang, et al., 2021). (Kalnaovakul & Promsivapallop, 2021) found that night market is not only a place for shopping but also a harmonious combination of tourists’ experiences in terms of cuisines, products, souvenirs, cultural items, and street performing arts. With such a variety of approaches to night market definitions, in this article, night market is a destination for tourist to experience typical night time activities namely walking, sightseeing, enjoying street food, shopping for garments, local specialities, and souvenirs, etc. According to (Baker & Crompton, 2000) “Satisfaction is a psychological feeling of a customer after experiencing a service or product”. (Caruana, 2002) “Tourists’ satisfaction is an emotional reaction after experiencing a service or product”. When tourists are interested in a product or service, they show their satisfaction (Fen & Lian, 2007). “Satisfaction is a feeling of enjoyment or disappointment of an individual when comparing their practical experience (actual results) with desire (expectations) about a product or service”. Based on different definitions of customer satisfaction, it can be concluded that “Tourists’ satisfaction with the night market is a psychological reaction to actual experience with such activities as walking, sightseeing, enjoying street food, shopping for clothes and garments, local specialities, and souvenirs, etc. at the night market”. This conclusion is similar to research findings of (Yoon & Uysal, 2005); (Del Bosque & San Martín, 2008); (Ramkissoon, et al., 2012).

2.2. Research model

The research model of this paper is developed with reference to a number of service quality models, *i.e.* 4 out of 5 factors in the 5-component (factor) service quality model suggested by (Parasuraman, et al., 1988); 3 out of 5 factors in the service quality model suggested by (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000), (Lee, et al., 2008); (Thin & Huy, 2014); (Sardar, et al., 2020); (Chi & Qu, 2008); (Kung, et al., 2020); (Agustinawati & Yusuf, 2018).

The more diverse and plentiful food and beverages at night market are, the more likely it will meet tourists’ demands to explore regional specialities and increase their satisfaction level accordingly (Lee, et al., 2008); (Sardar, et al., 2020). Food and beverages at night market attract both local residents and tourists. (Hsiu-Jung Chou, 2013) in his research on Taiwan street food places indicated that local food has positive impacts on satisfaction levels of domestic and international tourists as well. Similarly, (Lim, et al., 2010) found that flavor-rich dishes have positive effects on tourists’ satisfaction.

Research hypothesis H1: Local specialities have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

According to the Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943), safety is one of basic needs of a person. Particularly, when traveling to a new destination, his need for safety will be higher than usual. In the case of night market, which is a public place with many people of different backgrounds, safety will be a concern for tourists and their companions. A research by (Tuan, 2015) in Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam, showed that safety has a strong effect on tourists’ satisfaction. Similarly, (Sardar, et al., 2020) found that the number of tourists to Bangladesh before and after July 1st 2016 (the July 2016 Dhaka attack in the Holly Artisan Bakery) decreased significantly. Therefore, safety – security is one of obligatory factors of tourist destinations, and night market as well, contributing to tourists’ satisfaction (Parasuraman, et al., 1991); (Thin & Huy, 2014); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H2: Safety and security have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

Landscape environment includes sanitation system; garbage collection; sound and noise of night market. Landscape environment is an important factor contributing to service quality to meet tourist’ demands of relaxation and leisure. Once service quality increases, tourists’ satisfaction increases as well, thus, enhancing attractiveness of the destination (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000). Research by (Sadat & Chang, 2016) indicated that landscape environment helps create competitiveness of a tourist destination. The more positive a tourist feels about landscape environment, the more likely their satisfaction increases (Lee, et al., 2008); (Zeithaml, et al., 2009); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H3: Landscape environment has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

Entertainment services include arts and recreational activities, etc. organised at the tourist destination or nearby locations. Research by (Agustinawati & Yusuf, 2018) showed that arts programmes are one of the factors creating attractiveness for a tourist destination and enhancing tourists’ satisfaction. The higher tourists’ recreational demands are met, the higher their satisfaction with the destination will be (Chi & Qu, 2008); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H4: Entertainment services have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

The goods and products at the Night market are diverse and of high quality which could be consumed directly or purchased as gifts or souvenirs. In this sense, products have positive influence on tourists’ satisfaction (Chi & Qu, 2008); (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000). A research by (Lee, et al., 2008) in Taiwan showed that tourists are interested in consuming products at night market; similarly, a research by (Thin & Huy, 2014) in Can Tho, Viet Nam indicated that products are one of the factors attracting tourists to visit and purchase things at night market.

Research hypothesis H5: Products have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

Facility is one of the crucial components contributing to good service quality to enhance tourists’ satisfaction (Parasuraman, et al., 1991). Facility is also a visible factor easily perceived and noticed. In fact, once facilities of a tourist destination are reasonably arranged and appropriately equipped, they would contribute to increasing the attractiveness of that destination and encouraging tourists to experience more and shop more (Thin & Huy, 2014); (Kerdpitak & Heuer, 2016); (Sadat & Chang, 2016); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H6: Facility has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

Service attitude is reflected in the behaviours, attitude, and friendliness of sellers or stallholders directly serving tourists at the night market (Kung, et al., 2020). Service attitude is also an important component contributing to good service quality to enhance tourists’ satisfaction (Parasuraman, et al., 1991). Accordingly, service attitude of sellers at the night market not only helps them sell goods but also affects tourists’ emotions and levels of satisfaction (Lee, et al., 2008); (Thin & Huy, 2014); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H7: Service attitude has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

The price of goods and service is the cost tourists have to pay for their goods consumption in general and at the night market in particular. According to (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000), the price of service could have a big effect on tourists’ perception of service quality and satisfaction. (Sardar, et al., 2020) found that reasonable price in destinations is an advantage to attract tourists. If they think that the price is affordable, the goods and service quality is worth the payment, and flexible pricing policies are in line with the principle of selling and buying, they will feel happy

and eventually, satisfied with the destination (Chi & Qu, 2008); (Lee, et al., 2008); (Thin & Huy, 2014); (Boit & Doh, 2014); (Aliman, et al., 2016); (Kung, et al., 2020).

Research hypothesis H8: Price (feeling on prices) has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.

Figure 1: Research model

III. DATA AND ANALYSIS METHODS

Investigating tourists’ satisfaction with tourist destinations in general and night market in particular is not a new research topic. This article is an empirical research with the research space of Son Tra Night market in Da Nang city, Viet Nam. Thereby, previous research findings are referred to as a basis to systemize theoretical foundation to formulate the research model of factors affecting tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang. This article focuses on using primary sample data with questionnaire and convenient sampling methods, in face-to-face format, for domestic tourists experiencing the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang in three months from September to November 2022. The sample results are detailed in Table 1.

To measure tourist’s satisfaction and factors affecting their satisfaction with Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, we used the 5-point Likert scale in direct proportion levels (the higher the levels of satisfaction are, the higher the scores will be). In order to ensure scale reliability of the factors, scale reliability analysis and exploratory factor analysis techniques are employed. In addition, multivariable regression analysis technique is used to estimate and test the effects of factors on domestic tourists’ satisfaction with Son Tra Night market in Da Nang-Viet Nam.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1. Research sample

Table 1: Data sample research

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	90	33.3
	Female	180	66.7
Age (year)	Under 25	79	29.3

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Occupation	25 - 45	165	61.1
	Over 45	26	9.6
	Students	72	26.7
	Civil servants	27	10.0
	Businessmen	107	39.6
	Retirees	7	2.6
	Others	57	21.1
Region of Viet Nam	North	82	30.4
	South	88	32.6
	Central	100	37.0
Total		270	100.0

Regarding sample structure by gender, there are 90 males (accounted for 33.3%), and 180 females (accounted for 66.7%). This structure is in accordance with gender characteristics of Vietnamese customers visiting supermarket, traditional market and night market.

Regarding sample structure by age groups, there are 79 customers under 25 years old (accounted for 29.3%); 165 customers from 25-45 years old (accounted for 61.1%); and 26 customers over 45 years old. This structure makes sense in a way that people from 25-45 years old tend to travel more often, thanks to having stable income, than other age groups. Those over 45 years old are more inclined to resort tourism while night market is mostly about exploration and shopping. This explains why this age group has the lowest percentage.

Regarding sample structure by occupation, there are 107 businessmen (with 39.6%) accounted for the highest

percentage as they visit the Son Tra Night market not only to experience but also to learn and discover business opportunities. Followed by group of students with 26.7% (72 people). This is reasonable because students are more inclined to explore and experience new things so it is easy for them to get attracted to crowded destinations like Son Tra Night market. In this sense, this sample structure is suitable with domestic tourists visiting the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang city.

Regarding sample structure by region, there are 82 tourists from the Northern region of Viet Nam (accounted for 30.4%), 88 tourists from the Southern region (accounted for 32.6%), and 100 people from the Central region (accounted for 37%). Despite such a difference, this sample structure is reasonable as localities in the Central region are closer to Da Nang than those in Northern and Southern regions.

In short, the surveyed sample, by gender, age groups, occupation, geographical areas, is totally 270 domestic tourists. According to (Kline, 2015), the research sample within the range of 200-300 is good. Meanwhile (Lee & Comrey, 2016) indicated that a sample of 200 observations meets research requirements. Also, according to (Hair, et al., 2006), sample represents the research population if the number of observation is five times the number of component questions in the questionnaire ($39 \times 5 = 195$). In this sense, the sample of 270 meets research requirements and ensures reliability in terms of representativeness to study tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam.

4.2. Results of scale reliability testing and exploratory factor analysis

Table 2: Results of scale reliability testing and exploratory factor analysis

No.	Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Initial Eigenvalues	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	Sig	Sums of Squared Loadings
1	Satisfaction	.950	4.173	0.903	0.00	83.467
2	Food specialities	.906	4.336			
3	Security	.895	1.601			
4	Environment	.856	1.066			
5	Entertainment	.911	5.753	.953	.000	73.662
6	Products	.923	2.529			
7	Facilities	.898	1.943			
8	Service attitude	.911	1.293			
9	Price	.918	7.367			

As can be seen from Table 2, Cronbach's Alpha values of 9 factors namely Satisfaction (at 0.950); Food specialities (at 0.906); Safety and security (at 0.895); Environment landscape (at 0.856); Entertainment services (at 0.911); Products (at 0.923); Facilities (at 0.898); Service attitude (at 0.911); and Price (at 0.918) are all greater than 0.6.

According to (Lavrakas, 2008), results of scale reliability analysis of 9 factors in the research model (Figure 1) including 8 factors affecting domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang are reliable enough to continue other analysis methods.

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The results of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) show that satisfaction factor and all other 8 factors affecting domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang have Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) values of 0.903 and 0.953 respectively, which are both greater than 0.5. Both Barlett’s sig. values are 0.000 (smaller than 5%). Minimum of Initial Eigenvalues value is 1.066 (greater than 1). Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings of both factors are

83.467% and 73.662% respectively (greater than 50%). Besides, loading values of 36 component questions (fewer than 3 compared to initially proposed scale) both greater than 0.5 (see Appendix 1). According to (Hair, et al., 2006) the exploratory factor analysis results (detailed in Table 2 and Appendix 1) are reliable enough to continue other analysis methods.

4.3. Results of regression analysis

Table 3: Results of model testing and assumption testing

Content	Tests	Sig
1. Model testing	Fisher	.000
2. Normality of residuals	One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov	.069
3. Residual mean	One-Sample	1.00
4. Autocorrelation	Runs	.394
5. Multicollinearity	VIF	6. Heteroskedacity (Spearman’s RHO)
		Sig
Food specialities	1.000	Food specialities
		.073
Safety and security	1.000	Safety and security
		.930
Landscape environment	1.000	Landscape environment
		.355
Entertainment services	1.000	Entertainment services
		.571
Products	1.000	Products
		.150
Facilities	1.000	Facilities
		.461
Service attitude	1.000	Service attitude
		.509
Price	1.000	Price
		.060

As can be seen from Table 3, Fisher test results show that the proposed research model is significant as sig value is 0.000 (less than 0.05); meaning with significant value of 5%, it can be concluded that at least 1 among 8 factors in the research model (Figure 1) affects domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam.

As the research model (Figure 1) is estimated and tested according to ordinary least squares (OLS) method, the research assumption has to be tested for the results to be reliable. The sig values of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov is 0.069 (greater than 5%) so the residuals of the model are normally distributed. The sig value of One-Sample test is 1 (greater than 5%) so the residual mean is 0.

The sig value of the runs test is 0.394 (greater than 5%) so the model autocorrelation does not exit. All VIF values corresponding to the 8 factors are smaller than 2 so Multicollinearity does not exit. All sig values of Spearman’s RHO test are smaller than 5% so there is no rank correlation between the 8 factors and model residuals, which means Heteroskedacity does not exit. All assumptions of the research model are not violated so the values of estimation and tests are reliable.

4.4. Findings and Discussion

Results of research hypotheses (see Table 4) show that all 8 sig values corresponding to 8 research hypotheses (detailed in Figure 1) are smaller than 5% so all 8 research hypotheses (namely H1; H2; H3; H4; H5; H6; H7; H8) are accepted.

Table 4: Results of research hypothesis testing

Research hypotheses	Standardized Coefficients Beta	Sig	Conclusion	Rank
H1: <i>Local specialities have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.203	.000	Accepted	7
H2: <i>Safety and security have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.184	.000	Accepted	8

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H3:	<i>Landscape environment has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.234	.000	Accepted	5
H4:	<i>Entertainment services have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.360	.000	Accepted	3
H5:	<i>Products have positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.242	.000	Accepted	4
H6:	<i>Facility has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.233	.000	Accepted	6
H7:	<i>Service attitude has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.388	.000	Accepted	2
H8:	<i>Price (feeling on prices) has positive effect on tourists’ satisfaction with night market.</i>	.409	.000	Accepted	1
R Square		.690			

The R Square, reflected in 8 factors: Food specialities; Safety – Security; Environment Landscape; Entertainment services; Products; Facilities; Service attitude; and Price, affecting domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam, is 69% and other factors not included in the model accounts for 31%. The Standardized Coefficients Beta of 8 factors is positive, meaning the factors have positive effect on domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam. In this sense, once tourists feel positive about the factors, their satisfaction levels would increase accordingly.

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Price factor is 0.409, thus, Price is the factor having the biggest effect on domestic tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market. This indicates that once products/service are set at a price that tourists feel worth the perceived value and payment, their satisfaction would be affected significantly. Price is most interested by tourists stemming from their spending ability and psychological reasons. In fact, Vietnamese people in general and tourists to Da Nang in particular are worried about being cheated when quality of the purchased product does not live up to its price as going on a holiday is supposed to be relaxing and experiencing new things not price gouging. In recent years when COVID-19 pandemic complicates spending ability of Vietnamese (Huong, 2022) and tourists to Son Tra Night market in Da Nang as well, therefore, price factor has the greatest effect on tourists’ satisfaction. This finding is similar to research findings of (Tuan, 2015); (Sang, 2015); (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000); (Sardar, et al., 2020).

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Service attitude factor is 0.388, ranked the second among 8 factors. The characteristic of products and service is that their processes of manufacturing and consumption happen simultaneously. In addition, the Son Tra Night market is the place where buyers and sellers have direct communication, accordingly, service attitude has a significant effect on satisfaction levels of people coming to the market in general and domestic tourists in particular. Besides, other factors contributing to

better service attitudes of sellers at Son Tra Night market could be hospitality of Da Nang people and close supervision of state management agencies. In fact, in all service businesses, service attitude has always been a factor with great effect on customers’ satisfaction (Hanif, et al., 2010); (Kung, et al., 2020).

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Entertainment service factor is 0.360, which is also a factor with great effect on domestic tourists’ satisfaction. An advantage of the Son Tra Night market is the diversity of entertainment services. The market is close to many must-see tourist destinations such as Dragon Bridge, Bridge of Love, Han river bank, etc. which makes it easy and convenient to sightsee. In fact, one of the original purposes of establishing the Son Tra Night market project was to entertain tourists at night time. In this sense, quality management and improvement as well as appropriate entertainment service development would enhance tourists’ satisfaction. According to research by (Chi & Qu, 2008); (Kung, et al., 2020), entertainment service is also a factor with great effect on promoting the image of the destination and tourists’ satisfaction.

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Products factor is 0.242, which shows that it is evaluated relatively good by tourists. In addition to relaxing and exploring experiences, tourists can buy a number of local products as souvenirs or gifts (Lee, et al., 2008), especially those with culturally rich features. In fact, products with typical regional features tend to attract more tourists (Tuan, 2015). At present, at the Son Tra Night market, there are 190 stalls selling food, craft goods, souvenirs, dried seafood, clothes, shoes, belt, wallets, and local specialities, etc. meeting diverse needs of tourists, thereby enhance their levels of satisfaction.

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Environment landscape factor is 0.234, which has relatively significant effect on tourists’ satisfaction. In fact, any improvements on environment quality will lead to enhancing tourists’ satisfaction levels (Sadat & Chang, 2016). Da Nang has an advantage of a young city whose population density is relatively low compared to general population density of Viet Nam (Huong, 2022). Besides, the city government has

issued guidelines and standards to develop as “a green – clean – beautiful city”, which has become a famous brand of Da Nang, thus, the environment landscape of Son Tra Night market is also managed according to these guidelines and standards. In this sense, the market benefits greatly from these advantages contributing to enhancing tourists’ satisfaction and promoting the attractiveness of Da Nang – Viet Nam as a well-known tourist destination.

Similarly, the Standardized Coefficients Beta of Facility factor is 0.233 affecting tourists’ satisfaction. The Son Tra Night market benefits greatly from transportation infrastructure and facilities of the city in terms of appropriate destination planning meeting necessary standards such as parking lots, public toilets, signposts, and stall decorations, contributing to improving tourists’ satisfaction.

Food specialities is a very important factor with tourists’ satisfaction as detailed in a research by (Lee, et al., 2008) on Taiwanese night markets. However, with Standardized Coefficients Beta value of 0.203, this factor only ranks the 7th out of 8 factors. The reasons might be because tourists already have dinner before visiting the night market as their biological eating time is around 5-7pm rather than after 8pm (the market becomes crowded and appealing at this time). In addition, Da Nang city is a destination famous for excellent seafood menus contributing to a variety of food choices for tourists. Accordingly, local specialities namely mì Quảng (Quang style noodles), tré (fermented pork skin), bánh khô mè (sesame dried cake), bánh in (print cake), etc. despite being long-standing well-known trademarks of the city, play insignificant roles in affecting tourists’ satisfaction with the Night market.

The Standardized Coefficients Beta of Safety-Security factor is 0.184, ranking the lowest position among the 8 factors. This may stem from the risk-taking mentality of tourists when visiting crowded spots like the night market. They tend to accept the crowd and noise and problems related to overcrowding in well-known tourist destinations (Tuan, 2015). Besides, the city policies of “5 No’s; 3 Yes’, and 4 safe-related programmes” (Trang, 2022) have long-standing and far-reaching effects on promoting its image as a safe, peaceful and liveable destination. As a result, safety-security does not have breakthrough effects on tourists’ satisfaction. This finding is also reasonable accordingly.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings indicate that all 8 factors in the research model have positive effects on tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam. This is an experimental evidence with a high level of reliability for the city authorities to make decisions related to improving service quality of the night market. Also, this article formulates 2 component questions namely FS4 and PR4 (Appendix 1) for future research to study more about tourist destinations in general and night markets in particular.

Nevertheless, this article has some limits. The COVID-19 pandemic was not included as a factor affecting tourists’ satisfaction with the night market. The survey time is only three months not full year round. Research on behaviours of international tourists, one of key groups of tourists to Da Nang, has not been conducted. Moreover, fluctuations in tourists’ satisfaction levels with the Son Tra Night market with reference to time series or before and after COVID-19 pandemic complications.

Accordingly, the future research development could be studying tourists’ satisfaction with the night market before and after COVID-19 pandemic complications; diversifying survey time to ensure higher representativeness of research sample in terms of time and regions of respondents; and studying international tourists’ satisfaction with the Son Tra Night market in Da Nang, Viet Nam.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire

No.	Code	Content	Loading factor	Source
1	SA1	I like going to the Night market.	.899	(Aliman, et al., 2016)
2	SA2	I am satisfied with my decision to go to the Night market.	.911	(Aliman, et al., 2016)
3	SA3	I have positive feelings going to the Night market.	.911	(Aliman, et al., 2016)
4	SA4	The visit to Night market is better than I expected.	.924	(Aliman, et al., 2016)
5	SA5	The decision to go to Night market is appropriate.	.923	(Boit & Doh, 2014)
1	FS1	There are a variety of local famous junk food at Night market.	.789	(Lee, et al., 2008)
2	FS2	There are a variety of local typical beverages at Night market	.768	(Lee, et al., 2008)
3	FS3	The Night market gives me chances to experience local cuisine.	.678	(Kung, et al., 2020)
4	FS4	There are many seafood dishes at the Night market.	.702	Authors’ suggestion
1	SS1	The Night market is clean.	.548	(Sardar, et al., 2020)
2	SS2	Food hygiene and safety is ensured at the Night market.	.570	(Sardar, et al., 2020)
3	SS3	There are no pickpockets and robberies at the Night market.	.729	(Sardar, et al., 2020); (Thinh & Huy, 2014)
4	SS4	There is a regular security force at the Night market.	.664	(Thinh & Huy, 2014)

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1	LE1	The air quality at Night market is fresh	.626	(Sadat & Chang, 2016)
2	LE2	The sound of electronic devices at Night market is appropriate.	.647	(Sadat & Chang, 2016)
1	GT1	There is a mix of traditional and modern musical cultures at the Night market.	.613	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
2	ES2	There are exciting recreational activities at the Night market.	.614	(Kung, et al., 2020)
3	ES3	There are many entertainment spots connected with the Night market.	.669	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
4	ES4	I feel excited visiting the Night market.	.675	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
5	ES5	There are interesting painting experiences at the Night market.	.730	(Agustinawati & Yusuf, 2018)
1	PR1	There are clothes stalls at the Night markets.	.730	(Lee, et al., 2008)
2	PR2	There are typical local products at the Night market.	.722	(Lee, et al., 2008)
3	PR3	There are interesting products at the Night market.	.778	(Lee, et al., 2008)
4	PR4	There are many activities to make traditional products.	.688	Authors’ suggestion
1	FA1	There is a public parking lot for tourists at the Night market.	.596	(Kerdpitak & Heuer, 2016)
2	FA2	There is a clean public toilet at the Night market.	.742	(Kerdpitak & Heuer, 2016); (Sadat & Chang, 2016)
3	FA3	The stalls are arranged and decorated beautifully at the Night market.	.745	(Kerdpitak & Heuer, 2016)
4	FA4	There are suitable signposts at the Night market.	.698	(Lee, et al., 2008)
1	AS1	Sellers at the Night market have an attentive service attitude.	.630	(Kung, et al., 2020)
2	AS2	Sellers at the Night market have a friendly service attitude.	.598	(Kung, et al., 2020)
3	AS3	Sellers at the Night market feel happy when I bargain for their goods.	.690	(Lee, et al., 2008)
1	P1	The price of goods at the Night market is reasonable.	.656	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
2	P2	The price of food at the Night market is reasonable.	.775	(Lee, et al., 2008)
3	P3	The value of goods at the Night market is worth its price.	.742	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
4	P4	It is easy to bargain for products at the Night market.	.756	(Chi & Qu, 2008)
5	P5	There is no price discrimination between local visitors and tourists at the Night market.	.523	(Lee, et al., 2008)